

School Management Practices And Teachers' Job Performance In Public Senior Secondary Schools In Akwa-Ibom State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between school management practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State. The study was guided by three objectives, each with corresponding research questions and hypotheses. It adopted a correlation research design. The population of this study comprised 7,026 teachers across 231 public senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State. The sample size was 702 respondents, representing 10% of the entire population. The study employed a proportionate stratified sampling technique. The instruments, titled School Management Practices Scale (SMPS) and Teachers' Job Performance Scale (TJPS), were utilized for this research. These instruments were validated, yielding reliability coefficients of 0.87 and 0.84 for the School Management Practices Scale and the Teachers' Job Performance Scale, respectively, using Cronbach's alpha. The research questions were addressed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation, and the same correlation statistics were employed to test the corresponding hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05 with the assistance of SPSS. The findings revealed that strategic planning and communication practices strongly and significantly relate to teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State. Additionally, team building, staff involvement, instructional supervision, and capacity-building program practices moderately and significantly relate to teachers' job performance in these schools. However, motivation practices insignificantly relate to teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State. Based on these findings, it is recommended, among other things, that principals, as managers of secondary schools, should make efforts to implement measures that enhance teachers' contributions to teamwork and express gratitude to those who demonstrate exemplary behaviour and make sacrifices for the success of teamwork in the school.

Keywords: School, Management Practices, Teachers' Performance

INTRODUCTION

Education could be seen as an instrument for achieving socio-economic and technological growth and development of any nation. It is an instrument par excellence and the means of developing human intellect, technical skills, character, and effective citizenship for self-reliance and effective national development (FRN, 2014). A simple way of appreciating education is that it is a tool or a necessary weapon that is needed by every human being in order to effectively navigate this complex world (Aguba, 2021). Education, in essence, is the most effective tool for academic progress, social mobilization,

political survival, and effective national development of a country; it constitutes the single largest enterprise in Nigeria.

The educational policy of any nation is to achieve Education For All (EFA). The priority is to ensure equitable access and improvement in the quality and efficiency of all levels of education. Therefore, it is typical for an educational institution to sufficiently provide for its clients (parents, students, society, employers of labour, and other stakeholders), through the teachers, who are the direct channels through which educational objectives can be transmitted to learners. The school management is saddled with the task of overseeing the activities of students, and teachers for the actualization of the educational objectives of the nation.

However, for education to strive along with the recent pace of development, the school management need to adopt practices that can help the school to achieve optimal results and as well improve teachers' performance. The school management from time to time has to carry out checks to identify areas that need to be improved upon through innovative practices so as to ensure teachers productivity. The school management as a change agent in the school needs to be foresighted in all efforts to initiate activities in order to endure performance in schools especially from the teachers who are the implementers of educational policies. The inability of the school management to be proactive and innovative in its practices impedes the standard of secondary education.

School management practices are crucial for the general development of the school organization. They are principles and techniques expected of those at the helm of affairs of the school (Azowa & Tantua, 2020). It is a whole new scientific area because it combines law, theory and politics as much as philosophical and historical documents. Management practices provide guidelines for acceptable behaviour by organizations in both their strategy formulation and day-to-day operations. In the case of the secondary school, they are all aspects of school workplace conducts put up by the principal who is the leader in the school in ensuring proper administration of the school system. Hence, the school principal is held responsible for how the teachers teach, and how well the students learn.

Jones, et al (2020) stated that school management practices govern the behaviour of the school organization with respect to what is right and what is wrong in the school. It spells out the basic viewpoint and priorities of the school in concrete terms. It also contains the prohibitory actions at the school. It provides a framework on which the school could be legally governed. In other words, how well the school adhere to management standards and practices initiated by the principal, obviously, determines the well-being of all the stakeholders, the teacher performance and the subsequent profitability in the administration of the school, as well as the macroeconomic growth and development of the nation the school finds itself (Adeyeye, et al., 2018). These school management practices initiated by the principal who is the chief administrator of the school are therefore designed to increase the output, efficiency of learning, and to improve learning outcomes. Some of these practices according Okoringa (2018), Amadi and Udisi (2021) are team building, strategic planning, staff involvement, instructional supervision, capacity building programmes, communication and motivation practices

Team building as define, involves matching the right people and materials together to ensure that the best service is derived from the team. The principal is in a better position to merge teachers together when there is need to carry out an essential duty so as to ensure that the best outcome is attained. The principal can therefore use the team building practice to control the quality of work done by the teacher. During this process, the principal can either bring the best teachers together as a team or merge experienced teachers with less experienced ones so as to be able to achieve quality job performance from the team. Erawan as cited in Chantathai, et al (2018) stated that planning, operation, evaluation, and decision making in school development require active teamwork. This fortunately is a necessity for teachers to discharge their duties professionally.

The principal can also apply strategic planning as a practice. In this case, the principal makes proper forecasting of how work must be done by the teacher or any other staff so as to ensure that quality service delivery is achieved. The teacher in collaboration with other experts can draw the work schedule of the

teacher and ensure that the teacher works in line with the plan on ground. Doing this will help the teacher to improve in their job performance since the end product of the plan is that the quality of service provided by the teacher meets with best practices. The principal must however ensure that the plans made in the school are adhered to by all teachers so as to ensure that the goals and objectives of the plan are achieved as they relate to the school system (Azowa & Tanta, 2020).

performance in that process. Involving the teacher as a staff in school activities will therefore expose the teacher to ways that work must be done in the school so as to sustain the quality of educational services provided in the school (Jones et al., 2020).

Instructional supervision is the process of helping, guiding, and stimulating growth in a teacher in order to improve performance. It brings about a qualitative and quantitative improvement in instructional delivery in the teaching learning process. It is a means by which the principal being the management head guide and mentor teachers in order to ensure improved performance. Capacity building programmes refers to the process of developing qualities in teachers that will enable them to be more productive and thereby contribute more to school organizational goal achievement. Communication is the process of transmitting one's thoughts, ideas, wishes, attitudes, and emotions to others. Communication is central in any institution, and it is the "live wire" of any given institution, and the source through which the goals, and aspirations of any institution can be transmitted.

Motivation is the process of arousing, directing, and maintaining behaviour towards the achievement of a particular goal. Teachers could be motivated by factors in the external environment such as salary, job security, allowances, trainings, workshops, conferences, and bonuses which is extrinsic, and when teachers are motivated by the love they have for the job or task it is intrinsic motivation. The above mentioned are practices that can be adopted by a principal to increase quality, output and teachers' job performance.

Teachers' job performance is contingent upon intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, if there is management of good personnel, good infrastructure and culture climate, teaching materials and good supervision. Twomey and Jennings (2021) argue that teacher performance can be determined by practices and activities introduced by the principal in the school. Teachers who are not well motivated by the practices of the principal who is at the hem of affairs of the school, do not perform as expected since they do not see the value of their work. Robert, et al (2021) asserted that the performance of the teacher is also hinged on the physiological, and mental strength as well as the physical environment in which he finds himself. Physical environment here refers to the workplace of the teacher and all the practices that take place there. Performance, according to Robert, et al (2021), could be described as an act of accomplishing, or executing a given task. Teachers' job performance is determined by the teachers' level of participation in the day-to-day running of the school. However, since teachers behave differently under different situations, it rests on the school management to encourage effective performance of teachers through identifying their needs and satisfy them. Indices of teachers' job performance include regular and early reporting at school, adequate teaching preparation, competence in subject, adequate lesson presentation, effective supervision of student, participation in extra curricula activities, acting as in-loco-parentis to students, disciplinary ability among others. However, it could be observed that, teacher performance has declined in recent times in public senior secondary schools due to lots of factors such as; poor remuneration and conditions of service, and inadequate recognition of teachers' worth in society, a factor that really needs to be taken into consideration is the practices of the school management towards the teachers (Owence, et al., 2018).

Ray-offor (2021) opined that some teachers have negative perceptions about school management, and this has led to their poor performance and laissez faire attitude on their work. According to the scholar, school management practices have a high propensity to influence teachers' commitment to a high performance expectation, intellectual stimulation, communication, personal recognition, and supportive leadership. The importance of this is that, school management practices can give life to a school, and give staff and learners a sense of belonging, emotional stability, as well as recognizing the needs of staff and

students, thereby commanding loyalty and commitment, and by so doing improve performance among teachers. Ray-offor (2021) further stated that, teachers' performance can be high in some schools and poor in others. This could be a function of the school management practices and other factors, and this has resulted in the play of dynamics in such institutions. While in some schools, teachers put in their best because of the practices utilized by the school management as well as the conducive environment, in some other schools it is lacking, or where it exists, inadequate, hence, the poor performance of teachers. This study therefore examined the relationship between school management practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State.

Statement of the Problem

The desire of students in public senior secondary schools is to receive quality education. The government is also concerned with quality education that could help in producing quality people, who may become useful in the society in so many ways. Teachers are the vehicle through which quality education can be transmitted to students for useful living. This justifies the notion of no educational system may rise above the quality of its teachers. Teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools has been a cause for concern, particularly, among stakeholders in the education industry in recent times. Issues affecting teachers' job performance seems to be on the high side as the day goes by owing to lots of factors such as; lack of supervision, inadequate training, lack of digital skills, ineffective communication and poor welfare.

Nevertheless, one factor that has not really been taken into consideration is the practices of the school management towards the teacher. Many teachers have negative perceptions of their school management and are linking their poor performance to bad school management practices. The researcher personal experiences, resulting from his interrogation with some teachers in the state, the blame many a time goes to the state government, citing poor funding and lack of concern on school issues. However, they exonerate the school management headed by the principal to share in the blame. Now, the questions being asked is; could it be that school management are not allowed to initiate measures outside "prescribed" guidelines in working with teachers without seeking approval from government even when such measures are geared towards teachers' job performance? This unanswered question and many others prompt the investigation of this study on the topic "school management practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State."

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to examine the relationship between school management practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State. Specifically, the objectives of the study sought to:

1. Determine the relationship between team building practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State.
2. Ascertain the relationship between strategic planning practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State.
3. Fine out the relationship between staff-involvement practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guide the study:

1. What is the relationship between team-building practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State?
2. What is the relationship between strategic planning practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State?
3. What is the relationship between staff-involvement practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between team-building practices and teachers’ job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State.
2. There is no significant relationship between strategic planning practices and teachers’ job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State.
3. There is no significant relationship between strategic planning practices and teachers’ job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a correlational research design to ascertain the relationship between the dependent variable (teachers’ job performance) and the independent variable (school management practices). The population of this study comprised 7,026 teachers (3063 male and 3,959 female) in 231 public senior secondary schools across the 31 Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State. The sample size for this study was 702 respondents, representing 10% of the entire population. A proportionate stratified sampling technique was used for the sample selection. The questionnaire served as the data collection instrument for this study, consisting of two sets titled: School Management Practices Scale (SMPS) and Teachers’ Job Performance Scale (TJPS). The instrument consists of three sections: A, B, and C. Section A includes the demographic information of the respondents, while Section B contains questionnaire items on SMPS. The second instrument, Section C, addresses questionnaire items on TJPS. Both SMPS and TJPS were structured using the 4-point Likert rating scale: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points, Agree (A) = 3 points, Disagree (D) = 2 points, and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 point. The reliability coefficients of the instrument were computed using SPSS Version 23, yielding coefficients of 0.87 for the School Management Practices Scale and 0.84 for the Teachers’ Job Performance Scale. The research questions were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation, and hypotheses were tested using the same correlation statistics.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between team-building practices and teachers’ job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State?*

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between team-building practices and teachers’ job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State.

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis Showing the Relationship between Team Building Practices and Teachers’ Job Performance in Senior Secondary Schools in Akwa-Ibom State.

Variables	N	df	R	p-value	Decision
Team Building	683	681	0.412	0.000	Rejected Ho ₁ (Significant)
Teachers’ Job Performance	683				P < 0.05

Decision Rule: 0.00 – 0.19 = Very Weak, 0.20 – 0.39 = Weak, 0.40 – 0.59 = Moderate, 0.60 – 0.79 = Strong, 0.80 – 1.00 Very Strong

To answer the research question 1, results from Table 1. produced a correlation coefficient, ‘r’ of 0.412, which by percentage is 41%. This value shows there is a moderate and positive relationship between team-building practices and teachers’ job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State. This implies that team-building practices initiated by the principal correlate with teachers’ job performance.

For hypothesis 1, it is also revealed from Table 1 that the correlation for hypothesis one shows a significant correlation at $r = .412$, where $p\text{-value} = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$). Since the $p\text{-value}$ of 0.000 is less than the alpha value of 0.05, we therefore reject the null hypothesis, thus, there is a significant relationship between team building practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between strategic planning practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State?*

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between strategic planning practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State.

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis Showing the Relationship between Strategic Planning Practices and Teachers' Job Performance in Senior Secondary Schools in Akwa-Ibom State

Variables	n	df	r	p-value	Decision
Strategic Planning	683	681	0.611	0.000	Rejected H_{02} (Significant)
Teachers' Job Performance	683				$P < 0.05$

Decision Rule: 0.00 – 0.19 = Very Weak, 0.20 – 0.39 = Weak, 0.40 – 0.59 = Moderate, 0.60 – 0.79 = Strong, 0.80 – 1.00 Very Strong

To answer the research question 2, results from Table 2 produced a correlation coefficient, 'r' of 0.611, which by percentage is 61%. This value shows there is a strong and positive relationship between strategic planning practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State. In other words, strategic planning practices correlate with teachers' job performance.

For hypothesis 2 tested, it is also revealed from Table 2 that the correlation for hypothesis two shows a significant correlation at $r = .611$ where $p\text{-value} = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$). Since the $p\text{-value}$ of 0.000 is less than the alpha value of 0.05, we therefore reject the null hypothesis, thus, there is a significant relationship between strategic planning practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State.

Research Question 3: *What is the relationship between staff-involvement practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State?*

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between staff-involvement practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis Showing the Relationship Between Staff-Involvement Practices and Teachers' Job Performance in Senior Secondary Schools in Akwa-Ibom State

Variables	n	df	r	p-value	Decision
Staff-Involvement	683	681	0.525	0.001	Rejected H_{03} (Significant)
Teachers' Job Performance	683				$P < 0.05$

Decision Rule: 0.00 – 0.19 = Very Weak, 0.20 – 0.39 = Weak, 0.40 – 0.59 = Moderate, 0.60 – 0.79 = Strong, 0.80 – 1.00 Very Strong

To answer the research question 3, results from Table 3 produced a correlation coefficient, 'r' of 0.525, which by percentage is 52%. This value shows there is a moderate and positive relationship between staff-involvement practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State. This implies that staff-involvement practices correlate with job performance.

For hypothesis 3 tested, it is revealed also from Table 3 that the correlation for hypothesis three shows a significant correlation at $r = .525$ where $p\text{-value} = 0.001$ ($P < 0.05$). Since the $p\text{-value}$ 0.001 is less than the alpha level 0.05, we therefore reject the null hypothesis, thus, there is a significant relationship between staff-involvement practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first finding of this study revealed that there is a moderate and positive relationship between team building practices and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State. This finding of the study is not surprising to the researcher because not every principal in schools under review set up teams that could assist them to deliver on their mandate of effective administrative practice. No wonder from the result it is revealed that team-building as management practice relate to teachers' job performance to a moderate level of just 40% in public secondary schools in the state. This result is in consonance with Ige, et al (2017) who reported that the absence of teamwork amongst staff in the school brings about failure of the school to coordinate works into work groups so as to tap from the respective human resources the school possesses. According to the scholars the absence of properly instituted teams or committee in the school to facilitate school activities will not only bring about poor performance of students but as well poor administrative system in the school. A team exists when individual strengths and skills are combined with teamwork in the pursuit of a common cause in order to produce meaningful results for the team members and the organization (Adeyeye, 2020).

The second finding of the study showed that there is a strong and positive relationship between strategic planning practices and teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State. This substantiation provided an account for the reasons of some improvement in job performance of some teachers in public senior secondary school in the state. This finding is tandem with Owolabi and Makinde (2012) who in their study found out that there is a significant positive correlation between strategic planning and personnel (teacher) performance. Weldon and Weingart (2018) concurred that strategic planning plays an important role in the goal effort of a school. According to the scholars, school activities are planned on daily, weekly, monthly, term and yearly basis by school administrators like curriculum planning, timetabling, conferences, seminars, examinations, graduation ceremonies, duty post schedules, teachers, students, sports, cultural days, school records organization, PTA and staff meetings, discipline, committee, school plant facilities, manpower, fund raising, supervisory and inspection activities and others are planned activities done by the school head and committee.

The third finding of the study revealed that there is a moderate and positive relationship between staff-involvement practices and teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State. Every organization that wishes to succeed must involve her staff in all her administrative activities. It is the staff that help in the implementation of management plans and as such they need to be involved in all decision making as their input will determine whether or not the staff will perform or not. This finding is in agreement with Sisson (2019) who in his study of direct staff participation and their performance, has been found that application of direct staff participation make a positive contribution to a range of indicators of their performance such as output, quality, and reduction in throughout time as well as reducing sickness and absenteeism. Affirming to this, Mahfuz (2021) in a study to determine the level of employee involvement and how teamwork amongst employees in Jordan contributes to performance, found that there is a significant effect of employee involvement and their performance. This means that staff effectiveness is enhanced by involving the staff in all administrative activities of the school.

CONCLUSION

Based on findings of the study, it was concluded that strategic planning, communication practices strongly and significantly relate to teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State. However, motivation practice insignificantly relates with teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Akwa-Ibom State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following are hereby recommended.

1. Principals who are chief managers of secondary schools should make effort to come up with measures that can boost teachers' contribution towards teamwork, and show gratitude to those who exhibit exemplary behaviours and sacrifices for the success of teamwork in the school. This practice will spur and motivate staff to perform optimally in their job.
2. The principal, as part of his managerial practice, should work with the teachers, the Ministry of Education, as well as professional bodies in the education sector to always come up with strategic plans that can enhance school operations so as to keep improving teachers' job performance.
3. Principals and teachers should encourage the introduction of a perfect staff involvement program amongst teachers and other staff in the school, specifically in regards to decision-making process so as to increase their awareness and to motivate them to act effectively on decisions reached.

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